

unreported. The polarographic studies of reduction of some other oximes in solution has been reported earlier^{2,3}.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using a Blich apparatus (capillary method) and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a JEOL FX-90Q FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analysis were obtained using Perkin-Elmer 240C, CH N analyser.

Cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone (both B.D.H.) were distilled. Dimethyl glyoxime (B.D.H.), benzil, benzoin and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (all E. Merck), were used as such. All the oximes (1-6) used for reduction were synthesised by reported methods^{4,5} and were purified by recrystallisation from ethanol or water. These oximes are known compounds and were characterised by their m.ps. and spectral data.

A 250-ml beaker equipped with a porous diaphragm and thermometer was used as electrolytic cell. Mercury pool (33.2 cm²) or lead sheet (16.0 cm²) was used as cathode and platinum foil inside the diaphragm served as anode. Cathodic chamber contained the oxime (0.01 mol) in aqueous or ethanolic HCl (5%, 150 ml) and the anodic chamber contained aqueous or ethanolic HCl (5%, 50 ml). The catholyte was stirred using a magnetic bar. Nitrogen gas was purged (~5 min) in the catholyte before electrolysis. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 5 ± 2° by ice-salt bath. The constant current electrolysis (0.2 A, c.d. 6 × 10⁻³ A cm⁻²) was carried for a period calculated for 4F per oximino group in a particular experiment. After electrolysis the catholyte was filtered and the solvent removed by mild heating. The white solid (the corresponding amine hydrochloride) thus obtained was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, derivatisation and spectral data: **1b**, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 290, 2 960-2 840, 1 690, 1 630, 1 600, 1 575, 1 550, 1 490, 1 450 and 1 380 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.36-2.24 (8H, m, 4 × CH₂), 4.33-4.57 (1H, m, CH), 6.18 (1H, br s, NH) and 7.39-7.90 (5H, m, ArH); **2b**, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 300, 2 940-2 840, 1 690, 1 620, 1 600, 1 570, 1 530, 1 450 and 1 370 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.24-2.18 (10H, m, 5 × CH₂), 3.72-4.06 (1H, m, CH), 6.03 (1H, br s, NH) and 7.03-7.60 (5H, m, ArH); **3b**, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 340, 2 960-2 830, 1 740, 1 600, 1 580, 1 450 and 1 375 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.21 (6H, d, 2 × CH₃), 2.70-2.84 (2H, q, CH), 6.30 (2H, br s, NH) and 7.54-8.06 (10H, m, ArH); **4b**, ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 550, 3 360, 2 960-2 840, 1 745, 1 600, 1 570, 1 490, 1 450 and 1 375 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.21 (1H, s, OH D₂O exchangeable), 2.87 (1H, d, *J* 14 Hz, CH), 3.63 (1H, d, *J* 14 Hz, CH), 6.66-7.51 (15H, m, ArH) and 8.12 (1H, br s, NH, D₂O exchangeable); **5a/6a**, δ (CDCl₃) 2.24 (1H, s, OH, D O exchangeable),

Electrochemical Reduction of Ketoximes of some Cycloalkanones and 1,2-Diones

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*Manuscript received 27 November 1989,
revised 31 October 1990. accepted 16 January 1991*

IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on the cathodic reduction of some simple aliphatic oximes to the corresponding primary amine, we describe here the preparative utility of the cathodic reduction of oxime of some cycloalkanones, 1,2-diones and benzoin. The cathodic reduction of these is hitherto

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2.84 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable), 3.00 (1H, d, *J* 14 Hz, CH), 3.03 (1H, d, *J* 14 Hz, CH), 3.51 (1H, d, *J* 14 Hz, CH), 3.66 (1H, d, *J* 14 Hz, CH) and 6.75–7.51 (26H, m, ArH and N⁺H₃/Cl⁻).

Results and Discussion

Cathodic reduction of various oximes (1–6) was performed for a period calculated for 4F per oximino group. In case of the oxime 4 and 5 the analysis of the product revealed that both the oximino and carbonyl groups undergo the reduction process and the total amount of current passed was about 6F mol⁻¹. The isolated product in each case was the hydrochloride salt of the corresponding amine.

The effects of current density (c.d.), temperature and cathode material on the yield of the reduced products formed from cyclopentanone oxime (1) and cyclohexanone oxime (2) were studied. The results (Table 1) show that yield of the product is maximum at c.d. 6 × 10⁻³ A cm⁻². When current density is increased the yield of the product decreases appreciably. It may be reasonable to assume that at higher current density, hydrogen evolution dominates, suppressing the actual reduction process. The yield of the product is maximum at optimum temperature 5 ± 2°. The increase of temperature decreases the yield. The effect of cathode material on the yield of the product was investigated and it was found that mercury was most suitable cathode for the reduction process.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CURRENT DENSITY (c.d.), TEMPERATURE AND CATHODE MATERIAL ON THE REDUCTION OF 1 AND 2 IN 5% HYDROCHLORIC ACID

Current A	c d × 10 ⁻³ A cm ⁻²	Cathode	Temp. (±2°) °C	Yield (%)	
				1a	2a
0.16	4.8	Hg	5	80	83
0.20	6.0	Hg	5	83	86
0.24	7.2	Hg	5	75	80
0.40	12.0	Hg	5	58	60
0.20	6.0	Hg	18	64	67
0.10	6.0	Pb	5	71	79
0.10	6.0	Pb	18	50	54

Typical *iE* curves for the cathodic reduction of oximes 1, 2, 4 and 6 in 5% hydrochloric acid are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Curve-1 shows the hydrogen evolution process for the electrolyte. Addition of oxime indicates the positive shift of cathode potential and a good depolarisation is maintained throughout the studied current density range. In the acidic medium, it is the protonated species, [C=NOH]⁺H⁺ that actually gets reduced^{2,3}.

The α-benzilmonoxime (*E*-isomer)⁷ on electrochemical reduction gave rise to a single stereoisomer of 2-amino-1,2-diphenylethanol hydrochloride while the β-benzilmonoxime and the α(±)-benzoinoxime afforded a mixture of stereoisomers as evidenced from the pmr spectral data. The analytical, physical and ir spectral data are given in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Polarisation curves for cathodic reduction of oximes at Hg: (1) 5% aqueous HCl, (2) 5% aqueous HCl and cyclohexanone oxime (1.13 g), (3) 5% aqueous HCl and cyclopentanone oxime (0.99 g).

NOTES

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF AMINE HYDROCHLORIDE (1a-6a)*

Cathode : Hg. c.d. = 6×10^{-3} A cm⁻², Temp. = $5 \pm 2^\circ$

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.* (°C) Found/(lit. ^a)	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	Mol. formula	N-Benzoyl derivative 1b-4b m.p.* (°C) Found/(lit. ^a)
1a	83	195-6	3 200-2 810, 1 600, 1 550, 1 500, 1 450, 1 390	C ₈ H ₁₂ NC1	158 (158-60)
2a	86	206 (207)	3 200-2 820, 1 600, 1 553, 1 490, 1 450, 1 390	C ₈ H ₁₄ NC1	147 (147)
3a	72	>250	3 220-2 800, 1 600, 1 500, 1 450, 1 380	C ₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	>250 (296-7)
4a	70	206-8 (210)	3 560, 3 200-3 100, 2 940-2 840, 1 640, 1 580, 1 553, 1 490, 1 310	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ NOCl	235-6 (236-7)
5a/6a	65/64	208-10 (210)	3 560, 3 200-3 100, 2 940-2 840, 1 640, 1 580, 1 553, 1 490, 1 310	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ NOCl	

*All compounds gave satisfactory results for C, H and N analyses. ^aRef. 6.

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Fig. 2. Polarisation curves for cathodic reduction of oximes at Hg: (1) 5% ethanolic HCl, (2) 5% ethanolic HCl and α -benzilmonoxime (2.25 g), (3) 5% ethanolic HCl and benzoinoxime (2.27 g).